

Research report

Secondment in Bucharest, Romania

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Introducción

During my stay in Bucharest my research has focused on exploring and analysing contemporary artistic jewellery projects, with an emphasis on craftsmanship, innovative design, recycled materials and sustainable alternatives.

The first week of my stay, I had the opportunity to visit Beia Consult International's¹ facilities. I was welcomed with a guided tour of the company, during which I was given a detailed explanation of the nature of their regular work, as well as their specific involvement in the RRREMAKER² project.

The main activities included visits to cultural institutions such as the city's most prominent museums and galleries, where I analysed contemporary art exhibitions and explored the use of recycled or reused materials from an artistic perspective. I also had the opportunity to visit the Assamblage National Jewelry Association, where, together with its director, David Sandu, I delved into the current panorama of the jewellery sector in the country and the initiatives that this association promotes to position the city as an international benchmark in contemporary jewellery, highlighting the Romanian Jewelry Week (ROJW) as a key catalyst in this field.

In addition, the coincidence of the stay with the Christmas celebrations made it easier to visit the main craft markets organised during this season in the city, spaces in which numerous artisan jewellers participate. This allowed me to establish contact with some of them and learn more about their work.

Reception at BEIA with Eng. Oana Orza, Dr. Eng. Cristina Dobre and Dr. Eng. Ec. George Suciu Jr. (R&D and Innovation Manager)

¹ See in: <https://beia.ro/>

² Reuse Reduce Recycle AI-based platform for automated and scalable Maker culture in Circular economy. See in: <https://www.rremaker.com>

Current context of contemporary jewellery in Romania

Bucharest has emerged in recent years as an international benchmark in the field of contemporary jewellery thanks to a combination of key factors. On the one hand, the city has developed a vibrant artistic and cultural scene that fosters innovation and creativity in disciplines such as jewellery.

In 2009 AUTOR³ was founded, a platform created specifically to promote contemporary jewellery as an art and design form. With the aim of supporting both emerging designers and established artists in the field of signature jewellery, encouraging creativity and innovation in the sector.

The annual Fair AUTOR is a trade fair for designer jewellery, where designers can show and sell their pieces directly to the public and buyers. It is one of the leading exhibitions and events dedicated to contemporary signature jewellery in Romania. Since its inception it has evolved to become a key venue celebrating creativity, unique design and craftsmanship in jewellery. The event is primarily a jewellery fair where jewellery designers from all over the world present their creations. Through Fair AUTOR, designers have the opportunity to showcase original and high quality pieces that stand out for their innovation and artistic techniques.

On the other hand, institutions such as the Assamblage National Jewelry Association⁴ (2015), led by prominent figures such as the aforementioned Romanian contemporary jewellery designer David Sandu, have also played a key role in promoting contemporary jewellery, not only within Romania, but also globally. These initiatives have put Bucharest on the international map as a meeting place for artists, designers and academics interested in exploring the boundaries of this art form. David Sandu explained to us first-hand how the Assamblage School project has played a key role in the evolution of modern Romanian jewellery. This institution has been the starting point for a new generation of designers who have transformed and revitalised the creative and cultural landscape over the past 15 years.

With this in mind, Assamblage created Romanian Jewelry Week (ROJW) in 2020, a multi-faceted event, which includes exhibitions, conferences, workshops, fashion shows and cultural activities. Like the fair AUTOR, this event celebrates and rewards excellence in jewellery design. Helping to put local jewellers on the map and promoting their connection to the global art scene. ROJW was born as an effort to position contemporary Romanian jewellery in the international context, promoting both local artisanal design and dialogue with creators from around the world.

In 2024, the book *Romanian Jewelry Week: 5 Years of Contemporary Jewelry* was published, a work that compiles a selection of the pieces exhibited throughout the five editions of this event since its inception. This book has become a valuable source of inspiration, as it brings together a wide variety of international references presenting innovative proposals and diverse materials in the field of jewellery creation.

³ See in: <https://dautor.ro/>

⁴ See in: <https://www.assamblage.org/>

There is a strong interest in buying handmade and personalised products in the country. This represents an opportunity for jewellers to showcase their skills and sell their creations to a public interested in unique, handmade items, which encourages the holding of numerous craft markets where contemporary jewellery is increasingly gaining prominence. Among these markets, the one that coincides with the Mărțișor festival, a cultural tradition celebrated mainly in Romania, Moldova and parts of Bulgaria, on 1 March, stands out. This holiday marks the beginning of spring and is associated with the rebirth of nature.

The term 'Mărțișor' comes from the Romanian word Martie, meaning March, and refers to a small garment or amulet given as a gift on this date. Generally, the Mărțișor is a braided rope of red and white threads, symbolising the connection between winter and spring, the balance between cold and warmth, and purity and strength. Red is believed to bring good luck and vitality, while white symbolises purity. And while traditionally these amulets were made of simple materials, contemporary designers recreate and interpret them using precious metals, stones, recycled materials and innovative approaches, bringing a modern twist to an ancient tradition.

However, contemporary Romanian jewellery is not only limited to markets and workshops, but also has a presence in museum spaces, as in the case of the Art Safari Museum. In particular, during the exhibition entitled Young Blood 3.0, dedicated to young Romanian women artists, I had the opportunity to see the jewellery works of Ecaterina Poca (*Genetic Memory I* (2024), above) and Claudia Pușcașiu (*Serendipity* (2024), below).

Methodology

Research methods

- Documentary analysis and visits to cultural institutions and events involving the jewellery and contemporary art sector.
- Semi-structured interviews with contemporary jewellers.
- Direct observation of creative and technological processes in the workshops.

Criteria for selection of jewellers interviewed

Professional background, use of recycled or innovative materials, and application of new technologies.
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Interview questions

A script of questions was drawn up which, far from functioning as a rigid and structured interview, was intended to serve as a guiding thread to guide the visits to the workshops. This script allowed the jewellers to address various concerns related to the concept of contemporary jewellery, their creative process and their vision of the sector in the country.

Background and motivations

Where are you from?

What did you study?

What brought you to contemporary handmade jewellery and how would you describe your professional evolution until today?

Inspiration and style

What is your biggest inspiration or motivation for your creative process?

What are the main characteristics that define your style? How do you make your pieces tell a story or convey a message?

Tradition and culture

Do you incorporate elements of traditional Romanian craftsmanship into your contemporary designs? How important is this cultural connection for you?

Concept of contemporary jewellery

How do you define the concept of 'contemporary jewellery' and how does it differ from other types of jewellery?

Materials used

What role do non-traditional or recycled materials play in your work?

Do you use innovative materials in your manufacturing process?

Can you share any significant examples of pieces where you have used such materials?

Sustainability

Do you consider sustainability in your work process? How do you integrate sustainability principles into your creative process and material selection?

New technologies

Do you apply new technologies in your working process? What contemporary technologies (such as 3D design, 3D printing, photogrammetry...) do you use in the design or production of your pieces?

How have these technologies transformed your creative approach?

Market impact and Global trends

How do you perceive the market interest in contemporary jewellery in Romania?

What international influences do you consider most relevant to your work?

Projection and Future

Where do you see contemporary handmade jewellery heading?

What role can the concepts of sustainability and technology play in its future development?

Development of the stay

Visits to jewellers' ateliers

During the stay, an effort was made to contact a large number of contemporary jewellers in and around Bucharest. However, due to the busy Christmas season, it was not possible to communicate with all of them. The following are those with whom it was possible to visit their workshops and with whom a conversation was held.

Gligor Kuzmanovski⁵

He is a contemporary jeweller originally from Macedonia, currently based in Bucharest. Among the artists interviewed, he stands out for adopting a more sustainable approach throughout his creative process, making his pieces from recycled, reclaimed and reused materials, such as recycled paper and cardboard from which he makes a modelling paste, as well as wood from leftovers from the work of acquaintances and colleagues in cabinetmaking and carpentry.

His pieces present a delicate balance between textures and organic forms, generating an imaginary of figures inspired both by the reality that surrounds us and by the artist's own experiences, which serve as a source of inspiration for his creative process. On other occasions, it is the very nature of the intrinsic forms of the material that acts as a catalyst for creation.

⁵ See in: <https://www.instagram.com/gligorwoody/>

Corina Gheorghe - ARTKIMIA – Art & Jewelry Studio⁶

For more than 10 years she has been creating jewellery with metal clay. She also has her own jewellery school in Bucharest where she teaches courses on the material and invites other artists to give workshops at her school. She is also the distributor of the Art Clay brand.

This innovative material, developed in Japan, facilitates a more sustainable jewellery production process. In many cases, the metal particles that make up this clay come from recycled sources, such as old jewellery or industrial waste. Thanks to the precision and level of detail it can achieve, material waste is significantly reduced compared to other traditional methods. It also encourages small-scale, artisanal production, which helps to reduce the supply chain and minimises environmental impact. Finally, the use of small-scale ovens means lower energy consumption than conventional industrial processes.

⁶ See in: <https://artkimia.com/en/>

Claudia Pușcașiu – SAKRA⁷

She employs traditional jewelry techniques working primarily with metal, especially silver, and natural gemstones. Her highly distinctive style is distinguished by the creation of ring collections inspired by geometric shapes, with a particular focus on the structure of the square, which acts as a mantra guiding her creative processes. These collections break away from the usual norm by presenting rings with a square structure instead of the traditional circles.

On certain occasions, she has resorted to 3D modelling and printing to create some ring moulds. Sustainability is to some extent present in her work, as she tells us: "I create jewelry using good quality precious materials and natural stones, designed to last and be worn for many years. My goal is to craft timeless, durable pieces that minimize waste and encourage long-term use."

⁷ See in: <https://www.instagram.com/sakrajewellery/>

Mesteshukar ButiQ is an establishment dedicated to the marketing of handcrafted products made in Romania, where you can find various creations in jewelry, textiles, ceramics, wood, basketry, among others.

The main jewellery production offered there comes from a workshop located on the premises itself, where the jeweller Khalid works, originally from Palestine and resident in Romania for 42 years.

His work process follows traditional techniques, but is influenced by contemporary trends and styles. The pieces he creates stand out for their emphasis on geometry and minimalism. Khalid works primarily with metals such as copper, brass and silver, and in some of his collections he incorporates ancient coins from various parts of the world, which he acquires through antique dealers.

⁸ See in: <https://mbq.ro/>

Visit to a ceramics atelier

Perhaps this visit to a ceramics workshop is a little off the line of research into jewellery, but it allows us to learn about the contemporary role of other sectors of craftsmanship in the country.

Anca Vintilă Dragu - Una ca Luna⁹

Anca Vintilă Dragu, is a visual artist specialising in ceramics. She works on ceramic objects from both a traditional functional point of view and from a contemporary approach. She is a member of the Galateea Group, which runs the Galateea Contemporary Art Gallery, focused on contemporary ceramics.

During the visit to her workshop we talked about her professional career as a ceramist and we talked about other current projects very much in tune with the RRREMAKER project, such as:

- Unwasting materials¹⁰. The ongoing research of designer Ana María Sand Jensen, based on the exploration and creation of new resources for the architectural context from a sustainable design. Exploring the creation of ceramic coverings from agricultural waste or food waste, among other waste.

- Nod Makerspace¹¹. It is the first makerspace in Romania (more specifically, Bucharest), with workshops equipped for various crafts, a fablab and a coworking space that encourages the creation, prototyping and commercialization of projects. It also houses the first materials library in the country, with more than 2,500 samples.

- TATAIEstudio¹². A design studio (Târgu Jiu, Romania) that combines art, design and technology, betting on digital manufacturing to create ceramic objects using 3D printers.

⁹ See in: <https://unacaluna.ro/en/home-en/>

¹⁰ See in: <https://www.instagram.com/annamaria.sandjen->

¹¹ See in: <https://nodmakerspace.ro/>

¹² See in: <https://www.instagram.com/tataiestudio/>

Visits to cultural institutions, workshops, shops and craft markets

This section presents a list of all the places visited during the stay in Bucharest, related to the research carried out.

Museums and galleries

- National Museum of Contemporary Art
- National Museum of Art of Romania
- Art Safari Museum
- Municipal Museum of Bucharest
- Ivan Gallery
- H'Art Gallery
- Romanian Cultural Institute
- Sector 1 Gallery
- IOMO Gallery
- Horizont Art Gallery
- Calea Victoriei 91 Gallery
- Galatea Gallery (Contemporary Ceramics)
- Mobius Gallery
- Galateca Gallery

Associations

- Assamblage National Jewelry Association

Contemporary local craft shops

- Luvart
- Mesteshukar ButiQ

Jewelry ateliers

- Gligor Kuzmanovski
- ARTKIMIA – Art & Jewelry Studio – Corina Gheorghe
- Claudia Pușcașiu – SAKRA
- Mesteshukar ButiQ jewelry atelier

Ceramic atelier

- Ceramist Anca Vintilă Dragu

Markets and fairs where I have been able to make contact with jewelers

- Fair Dichisar
- Market Common House
- NÖEL Market
- Bucharest Christmas Market

Conclusion

During my stay in Bucharest, several key aspects of the contemporary jewellery field have been addressed. Visits to cultural institutions, workshops and markets have provided a detailed and varied insight into the current state of the sector in Romania. The city of Bucharest has emerged as a leading international hub in the field of designer jewellery, thanks to events such as the AUTOR Fair and the Romanian Jewelry Week, which foster creativity and innovation in jewellery design.

One of the most important findings of this research is the integration of recycled and sustainable materials in jewellery production, as observed in the works of jewellers such as Gligor Kuzmanovski and Corina Gheorghe. These approaches not only contribute to environmental sustainability, but also introduce new techniques and aesthetics into the art of jewellery making. The influence of new technologies on the sector has also been notable. The adoption of tools such as 3D printing and digital modelling has allowed jewellers to experiment with innovative shapes and structures, as in the case of Claudia Pușcașiu, who incorporates these technologies into her geometric designs.

Furthermore, direct contact with jewellers and artisans has revealed a deep commitment to the quality and durability of their pieces, reinforcing the idea of contemporary jewellery as a lasting and meaningful art form. This commitment is evident in the attention to detail and craftsmanship that each jeweller brings to their work.

In conclusion, contemporary jewellery in Bucharest is characterised by its dynamism and its ability to integrate tradition and innovation. The city has been able to position itself as an international benchmark in this field, attracting designers and buyers from all over the world. Sustainable practices and the use of new technologies are redefining the sector, opening up new possibilities for the creation and appreciation of unique and artistic jewellery.

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